

**STRUCTURAL GROUP ANALYSIS AND COMPARISON WITH CHARACTERISTICS JSC
"TRANSNEFT-SIBERIA" OILS BY ¹³C NMR SPECTROSCOPY**

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Abstract

The estimation of molar fractions of primary, secondary and quaternary, tertiary, aromatic groups, aromaticity factor and mean chain length of seven oils (JSC "Transneft-Siberia") based on ¹³C NMR spectra was carried out. The received parameters were analysed taking into account the kinematic and mass fraction characteristics of studied oils.

Keywords: ¹³C NMR spectroscopy; oil; functional group; qualitative analysis; quantitative composition.

1. Introduction

¹³C nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy has recently become increasingly popular as a tool for studying the characteristics of natural raw materials and their individual organic compounds ([1]; [2]; [3, 6942-6946]; [4, 1-9]; [5, 2858-2864]). NMR spectroscopy is used to study various petrochemical objects, expanding the possibilities for research in the field of geological and chemical problems ([6, 423-473]; [7]). The advantages of NMR spectroscopy are a reduction in the time taken for the analysis, and that it is a rapid and non-invasive process ([8]; [9, 464-475]; [10, 18-37]).

It is expected that in the near future, the development and application of NMR spectroscopy will help reduce the financial costs of heavy oil refining ([11, 280-281]; [12, 111-120]).

By using NMR, it is possible to analyze the chemical nature of individual types of hydrogen and carbon atoms, in various and complex mixtures of petroleum and in the final products obtained by refining processes ([13, 117622]; [14, 597-598]). In the NMR spectra, the functional groups of aromatics, aliphatics, and olefins can be fixed; accordingly, it is possible to differentiate a polynuclear aromatic from amononuclear aromatic and to identify the fuel physical properties by the concentration of aromatics and the chain length of aliphatics. The suitable information about the molecular carbon skeleton can be obtained by ¹³C NMR. This NMR technique is important for the structure elucidation and chemical composition of a sample. In addition, it distinguishes the existence of quaternary carbons of many functional groups, and produces spectra with well quality ([15, 1223-1227]; [16, 81-86]; [17, 151-123]). For this reason, ¹³C NMR has become one of the most important methods in the analysis of crude oil fractions.

The objective of this work is to carried out the comparison between original, kinematic, mass fraction and ¹³C NMR structural-group parameters of seven oils from JSC "Transneft-Siberia" company.

2. Materials and methods

NMR experiments on studied oil samples were performed on a Bruker Avance III HD 700 NMR spectrometer. The studied oil sample was diluted with deuterated chloroform. Field lock and shimming were achieved using the deuterium signal from CDCl₃ solvent.

¹³C NMR spectra were recorded using 90° pulses with broadband proton decoupling (pulse program zgig); relaxation delay between consecutive accumulations were 3.3 s (and acquisition time was 2.3 s); spectrum width was set to 220.0 ppm; number of scans was 1300. Exponential digital filter with the LB parameter of 10 Hz was applied prior to Fourier transformation. Measurements were made at the temperature of 25°C. All the NMR spectra were integrated after baseline correction, and a mean of minimum three integration values has been taken for each calculation. The relative standard deviation of the results of manual integration did not exceed 3%.

The characteristics of the studied samples from Table 1 were provided by the JSC "Transneft-Siberia" company.

3. Structural-group characterization and comparison with characteristics of JSC "Transneft-Siberia" oils of various origins by high resolution ¹³C NMR spectroscopy

The kinematic and mass fraction characteristics of studied oils are shown in Tables 1.

The structural-group analysis method with the data obtained from analysis the ¹³C NMR spectra to determine the oil composition we have already done before in our previous works ([18, 12-18]; [19, 256-262]; [20, 995]; [21, 8-12]; [22, 6-8]).

In this work, the estimation of molar fractions (%) of primary (C_p), secondary and quaternary (C_{sq}), tertiary (C_t), aromatic (C_{ar}) groups, aromaticity factor (F_{CA}) and mean chain length (MCL) of seven oils (JSC "Transneft-Siberia") (Table 2) based on ¹³C NMR spectra was carried out.

Table 1.

Characteristics of 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, 1.4, 1.6, 1.8, 1.9 (JSC "Transneft-Siberia") studied samples.

№	density at 20 °C, kg/m ³	kinematic viscosity at 20 °C, mm ²	mass fraction of mechanical impurities, %	mass fraction of water, %	mass concentration of chloride salts, mg/dm ³	mass fraction of sulfur, %	mass fraction of paraffin, %	mass fraction of asphaltenes, %	mass fraction of resins, %
1.1	838.7	7.33	0.0016	0.03	3.89	0.44	3.32	0.47	8.14
1.2	848.0	7.60	0.0021	0.03	8.37	0.46	2.87	0.43	7.87
1.3	850.5	8.31	0.0025	0.06	12.72	0.23	2.45	0.81	8.46
1.4	881.0	24.99	0.0058	0.09	6.01	2.1	2.52	0.99	9.72
1.6	863.2	13.48	0.0042	0.03	6.47	1.16	3.36	1.09	12.57
1.8	876.5	23.67	0.0058	0.17	21.08	1.53	2.98	1.19	13.59
1.9	833.7	5.45	0.0021	0.03	3.47	0.39	2.52	0.73	8.08

Table 2.

Molar fractions (%) of primary (C_p), secondary and quaternary (C_{sq}), tertiary (C_t), aromatic (C_{ar}) groups, aromaticity factor (F_{CA}) and mean chain length (MCL) of 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, 1.4, 1.6, 1.8, 1.9 (JSC "Transneft-Siberia") samples based on ¹³C NMR spectra.

Group type	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.6	1.8	1.9
C_p	17.4	22.8	20.6	20.0	20.6	19.7	22.0
C_{sq}	53.2	47.7	49.2	50.2	51.3	51.8	51.3
C_t	14.8	11.5	8.2	9.2	7.4	10.0	6.9
C_{ar}	14.6	18.0	22.0	20.6	20.7	18.5	19.8
F_{CA}	0.15	0.18	0.22	0.21	0.21	0.18	0.20
MCL	9.8	7.2	7.6	7.9	7.7	8.3	7.3

It is noted that an increase in density and kinematic viscosity parameters (Table 1) affects the decrease in the C_p parameter and the increase in the C_{ar} parameter (Table 2). It is also possible that the mass concentration of chloride salts (Table 1) leads to increased values of the C_{sq} parameter (Table 2). No correlations were observed between parameters such as mass fraction of mechanical impurities, mass fraction of water and mass fraction of sulfur with the parameters obtained by ¹³C NMR spectroscopy. Also, increased values of mass fractions of paraffins (Table 1) correlate well with increased values of the C_p parameter (Table 2). And an increase in the mass fraction of asphaltenes (Table 1) leads to lower values of the C_t parameter (Table 2). A correlation was observed between increased values of resin mass fractions (Table 1) with decreased values of the C_t parameter and increased values of the C_{ar} parameter (Table 2).

4. Conclusions

Using ¹³C NMR method, the structural-group characteristics of seven oil samples from JSC "Transneft-Siberia" company were determined and their correlations with the kinematic characteristics and various mass fractions of the studied oil samples were described.

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